

A New Explanation of Brightness Illusions: Unconscious Inferences of Light-Source Positions and Object Transparency by the Visual System

Seiyu Sohmiya
Sohmiya Institute of Psychology

Key words: brightness illusion, unconscious inference, light-source position

Purpose

It is well known that, in Figure 1A, gray patch A1 on a black background is perceived as brighter than the physically identical gray patch A2 on a white background ($A1 > A2$). This phenomenon is known as brightness contrast.

Brightness contrast has traditionally been explained by contrast theory and lateral inhibition. However, these ideas cannot account for all examples of brightness illusions. For example, in the White effect (Figure 1B), perception occurs in the opposite direction to that predicted by contrast theory. Specifically, rectangle B2, whose shorter sides are adjacent to black regions, is perceived as brighter than rectangle B1, whose longer sides are adjacent to black regions ($B2 > B1$).

Figure 1 Examples of brightness illusions.

Although many models have been proposed to explain brightness illusions without contradiction, no single model has yet been able to account for all known examples, and the debate continues. For example, the Anchoring Theory (Gilchrist et al., 1999) can explain brightness contrast, the White effect, and the checkerboard illusion shown in Figure 1C, in which C2 is perceived as brighter than C1 ($C2 > C1$). However, Bindman and Chubb (2004) argued that Anchoring Theory cannot explain the bullseye illusion shown in Figure 1D, in which D2 is perceived as brighter than D1 ($D2 > D1$). In response, Oh and Kim (2004) argued that the target region in the bullseye figure can be classified as belonging either to the black group or to the white group, and therefore the bullseye illusion should not be regarded as a counterexample to Anchoring Theory.

The author has shown (manuscript submitted) that both brightness contrast and the White effect can be explained by assuming that the visual system performs the following two forms of unconscious inference (Helmholtz, 1866):

- (1) Where is the light source located in the stimulus figure?
- (2) What does this figure represent in the real world? (Gregory, 1970)

Brightness contrast is explained as follows (see Figure 2). For the small circle a on a black background, the principal interpretations are five in total. If the visual system infers that the light source is located in front of the figure, three interpretations (a1–a3) are possible. If the light source is inferred to be behind the figure, interpretation a4 is obtained. If the light source itself is inferred to be the circle, interpretation a5 is obtained.

On the other hand, for the small circle b on a white background, the principal interpretations are b1–b5. Under interpretations a1–a5, the brightness of a is interpreted by the visual system as gray or light gray ($a \geq$ gray). Under interpretations b1–b5, the brightness of b is interpreted as gray or dark gray (gray \geq b).

Figure 3 Examples of the stimulus figures used in the experiment.

Next, the stimulus shown in Figure 3B was presented, and the observers were asked which achromatic color was most appropriate for regions b and b'.

Results

All observers judged that a and b should be black, whereas a' and b' should be white.

Discussion

The checkerboard illusion is explained as follows.

Among the ten possible interpretations shown in Figure 2, nine interpretations—corresponding to a1, a3–a5, and b1–b5, excluding a2—are possible as principal interpretations of region C2 in Figure 1C. However, the experimental results suggest that the visual system unconsciously infers that C2 should originally be black. If it is assumed that the visual system attempts problem solving (Rock, 1979) to explain why an object that should originally be black does not appear black, the interpretations corresponding to a1 and a3–a5 are selected from these nine possibilities.

Under interpretations a1 and a3–a5, the target region is interpreted by the visual system as gray or light gray. Therefore, the inferred brightness of C2 is gray or brighter ($C2 \geq \text{gray}$).

In contrast, the experimental results suggest that the visual system infers that C1 should originally be white. Accordingly, the principal interpretations of C1 correspond to b1, b2, and b4. Under these interpretations, the target region is interpreted simply as gray, that is, $\text{gray} = C1$.

Therefore, if the visual system selects at least one interpretation corresponding to a3–a5—for example, a3—the inferred brightness becomes $C2 > C1$, and C2 is consequently perceived as brighter than C1.

The brightness illusion observed in the bullseye figure can be explained in essentially the same manner.

If the author's explanation is correct, the results suggest that higher-level information processing is involved in brightness illusions.

The author believes that brightness illusions provide evidence for the importance of the perspectives proposed by Helmholtz, Gregory, Rock, and the Multiple Interpretation (MI) Hypothesis (Sohmiya, 2004) in the study of visual perception.

References

Bindman, D., & Chubb, C. Vision. Res. 44, 309–319 (2004); Sohmiya, S. Inferences of lightsSource positions and transparency in brightness illusions. (in submission).

(Sohmiya Seiyu)